

**PRINCIPLES OF USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL
TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC TEACHING**

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Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the principles of using innovative pedagogical technologies in bringing musical education to the key stage of development.

Key words: Principle, methodology, innovative pedagogical technology, music education, module, multimedia tools.

Introduction.

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies used in musical education can be any tool that can bring various types of information into educational activities. However, in most cases, when talking about technological tools, a computer and its surrounding equipment are understood. It is also permissible to list the multimedia tools used by teachers and students at school not only for texts or images, but also to work with audio or other information directly.

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies is a new computer-based approach to the educational process of elementary school students from a pedagogical point of view. Computer technologies are used as an important tool in increasing the activity of students, increasing the volume of studied educational materials, and increasing the level of efficiency of the educational process. It involves learning and building computer literacy using the materials displayed on the computer monitor. Innovative technological means is a set of hardware and software, which allows a person to communicate with a computer using various natural environments: sound, video, graphics, text, animation, etc. Innovative technology gives the user great opportunities to create a fantastic world (virtual reality), where the user does not play the role of a passive observer on the sidelines, but actively participates in the events unfolding there. At the same time, communication takes place in the language familiar to the user - primarily in the language of sound and video images.

Innovative technology tools include: audio (speech) and video input and output devices; high-quality sound (sound) and video - (video) cards, video capture cards (video grabber), which receive images from a video recorder or a video camera. Acoustic and video-receiving systems with high-quality amplifiers, sound speakers, large video screens, scanners that are now common

(because they allow automatic input of printed texts and images into the computer.

Video - (Lat. video - I look, I see) - is a component of compound words, which gives the meaning of connection to video signals, electrical signals that are added to the words. In addition, the image transmission system also refers to the systems and devices used in the videophone. Video recording is the recording of television, radio location and other image and sound signals on a magnetic tape, disc, magnetic recording or film tape and reflected in a photo-graphic recording. This information and communication tool allows you to save TV shows, video films, documentaries and artistic programs and replay them with sound whenever necessary. VCR video recording has many advantages over film recording, as it does not require the complex process of film processing, printing, and editing. The program can be shown in full, in part, here and there on the VCR. You can redo multiple times per tape. With the help of video, the problem of "time and space" is positively solved, because it does not "choose" the time, it does not "like" the place, that is, the video can be used anytime, anywhere.

Audiometry (lat. audio — I hear and ... metry), acumetry is the measurement of hearing acuity (good hearing). Since hearing acuity is mainly determined by the threshold of sound reception, audiometry consists in determining the lowest sound power perceived by the human ear. The simplest method of audiometry is to receive the sounds of a human voice at different distances or different pitches of a tuning fork. Audiometry is mainly performed with audiometers, special electric acoustic devices. In audiometers, the sound pitch (from 100 to 8000 gs) and power (from 0 to 125 db) are changed, and the sound is brought to the state of imaginary hearing (threshold of hearing). Audiometry results are recorded in the form of an audiogram (curve). You can access the Internet. During work on interactive whiteboards, students' attention will be improved, and as a result, the quality of modern education will be improved, students will improve their work performance.

Modern computer technologies provide great opportunities for the development of the educational process. At this point, it is permissible to quote the words of K. D. Ushinsky: "children's nature requires appearance." But it is not only diagrams, tables and pictures, but scientific and educational games, which are closer to children's nature.

Multimedia is a means of different knowledge in different classes. Multimedia helps to develop motivation, communication skills, acquire skills,

accumulate real knowledge, and also helps to develop information literacy. Media such as slide, presentation or video presentation has already become an old term, that is, it has been around for a long time. The computer now has the ability to manipulate audio and video to achieve special effects, synthesize and play audio and video, including animation, and combine them all into a single multimedia presentation. The rational use of visual educational tools in the educational process plays an important role in the development of students' observation, attention, speech, and thinking. The future of computer technologies in the school directly depends on how thoughtful the initial period of their introduction into the educational process is.

The first step is to create a media library by subject in schools. All schools create CDs in different subjects, which can then be used as a reference for self-study in that subject. The content of the lesson should be planned in advance. It is very convenient to use ready-made lesson plans, of which there are many today. Our media library should be located in an office equipped with a computer and a multimedia projector.

The main difficulty in preparing a specific lesson is that among the variety of "curriculum" programs, only an insignificant amount is related to the curriculum, the sequence of presentation of the material, terminology, content of the subject, course logic and determined by the lim standard. Modern multimedia encyclopedias, dictionaries, games with educational elements require special adaptation, the need for creative work of the teacher and methodologist, not counting specialized software developed by professional teachers in cooperation with teachers. does.

Therefore, we decide to use the capabilities of Microsoft PowerPoint in our work, which allows ordinary people in the field of computer science to quickly and easily create a series of information-rich slides, transformed into a single slide movie with multimedia effects.

Educational and control courses, presentation programs, computer lessons, created by the teacher are relatively interesting. First, they provide a methodologically correct presentation of the new material. Secondly, a strict sequence is observed in the presentation of the material according to the curriculum. Third, the didactic material used in their courses can be as varied as possible and updated as often as necessary.

Conclusion: no matter how complicated and boring the subject of the lesson is, if the educational materials on the screen are presented in colors, with sound and other effects, it will be interesting for the student.

The second step is to master the technology of creating a presentation for the lesson by the teacher. The most convenient and easy environment for creating such lessons is Power Point. The design of computer lessons begins with the creation of a calendar-thematic plan for studying the topic (the use of ICT tools is optimally distributed in all lessons)¹.

It takes into account the content of the studied material; basic pedagogical technology; availability of computers, software and audio-video tools in the educational process; psychological and sociometric characteristics of the group and each child; the need to replace various types of computer equipment, etc. For a specific computer lesson plan, the teacher:

- creates a temporary structure of the lesson, defines the tasks and necessary steps to achieve them;
- selects the most effective tools from the stock of computer supplies, considers the appropriateness of their use compared to traditional tools;
- the selected materials are evaluated in time: their duration should not exceed sanitary norms; it is recommended to review and prochronometerize all materials, taking into account the interactive nature of the material; it is necessary to properly plan the time reserve;
- collects the presentation program from the found materials (*files*).

For this he writes the script. In the presentation on the big screen, you can connect maps and diagrams, diagrams and photos, films and audio recordings - all this, if necessary, can be equipped with captions and comments, and the most important information with font, color and lighting. can distinguish. A computer "mouse" can be used as a pointer to direct students' attention to the most important areas on the screen; planning to achieve certain goals, provides their step-by-step and effective diagnosis. Using a computer allows for greater and deeper control. For this, a game program is used or an authoring program is developed that is included in the presentation program.

Conclusion: in the process of explaining new material, the presentation on the subject of the lesson allows the teacher not to write notes on the board, that is, there is more time for reinforcement.

The third step is to master the skills of working with multimedia programs by students. One of the ways to activate students' knowledge activities in classes is the ability to work with books and work on a computer, one of the most popular types of activities. Technology is mastered in design forms. Even a junior high school student can do a simple meaningful project in Microsoft

¹ Music in elementary school. Study guide. Compiled by G. S. Goncharova. Teacher, 1991.

Power Point. In the project activities, the student knows his task - he can reveal to others the importance of the methods of technological activity that he has mastered. He aims to develop skills in mastering the content of the desired topic, makes a step-by-step action plan, then displays it on working slides, and finally analyzes the result and the path leading to it.

Conclusion: the formation of skills for working with multimedia programs is the best tool in extracurricular classes or in groups with a small group of students. And it is these students who can later use the mastered programs to interest the rest of the class, because these software tools allow you to get as much educational information as possible with minimal costs.

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